

Case report

High-value microalgae production

supporting a circular and zero-waste bioeconomy

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Authors (Name, Short Org. Name)

Katrijn Van Laere, ILVO
Elke Vereecke, ILVO
Bert Coleman, ILVO
Johan Robbens, ILVO
Sofie Van Nerom, ILVO
Evelyne Delezie, ILVO
Praveen Kumar Ramasamy, DTI
Jakob Skov Pedersen, DTI
Yasmine Ambrogio, Universität Bayreuth
Detlef Bartsch, BVL
Jens Kahrmann, BVL
André Friedrich, BVL
Kai Priesnitz, BVL
Nicola Consmüller, BVL
Katharina Unkel, BVL
Irene Gallego, Agroscope
Joerg Romeis, Agroscope

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
EU	European Union
DW	Dry Weight
PBR	Photobioreactor
HVC	High Value Compounds
MAA	Mycosporin-like Aminoacids
NGT	New Genomic Techniques
CRISPR	Clustered Regulatory Interspaced Short Palindromic Repeats
Cas	CRISPR-associated (nuclease)
NHEJ	Non-Homology End Joining
HDR	Homology Directed Repair
ZEP	Zeaxanthin epoxidase
VDE	Violaxanthin deoxidase
VDL	Violaxanthin deoxidase-like
CFU	Colony Forming Unit
PEF	Pulsed Electric Field
BG	Blue Green (BG-11 medium is one of the most used for microalgae)
DO	Dissolved Oxygen
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
GMO	Genetically Modified Organism
CA	Competent Authority
RA	Risk Assessment
EC	European Commission

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Key messages

1. Microalgae offer a sustainable and efficient alternative for producing bio-based products, including food, feed, biofuels, and pharmaceuticals, with lower environmental impact compared to traditional agriculture.
2. Microalgae are rich in essential nutrients, including proteins, omega-3 fatty acids, vitamins, pigments, and antioxidants. Among others, microalgae are a natural and sustainable source of high-value carotenoids, such as astaxanthin, zeaxanthin, and lutein, which have many applications in pharmaceuticals, nutraceuticals, dietary supplements, cosmetics, and functional foods and feeds to support both human and animal health.
3. Microalgae offer many opportunities for dual-purpose use, i.e., the extraction and use of high-value compounds, such as carotenoids, and repurposing the residual biomass as feed additive for poultry. The main challenges for the use in poultry feed include the digestibility of the microalgae due to a rigid cell wall and the search for the most optimal inclusion rate in the feed formulation guaranteeing good digestibility and without compromising on beneficial health effects.
4. Advances in new genomic techniques, synthetic biology, and cultivation techniques are unlocking new possibilities for enhancing high-value compound production and optimizing biochemical composition for various applications.
5. The microalgae industry is growing, with increasing interest from multiple sectors. Scaling up production while maintaining cost-effectiveness remains a key challenge that requires continued investment and innovation.
6. Despite their potential, regulatory constraints, technological limitations, and high production costs still pose challenges for widespread commercialization. Addressing these barriers will be essential for the future success of the microalgae sector.

1. Introduction

Microalgae are a diverse group of eukaryotic aquatic organisms that thrive in fresh, brackish, or marine water, with over 200,000 species classified in various phylogenetic groups (Coleman et al. 2024). Microalgae can grow photoautotrophically, using light as an energy source to assimilate CO₂ for biomass production, or heterotrophically, using an organic carbon source for energy. Some species can also grow mixotrophically, using both light and organic carbon sources. Microalgae are considered as **promising raw materials for a biobased economy** as they yield high-value biomass (Figure 1), produce high-value compounds (HVC), such as pigments, vitamins, lipids, and mycosporine-like amino acids (MAAs) (figure 2), and also play a role in CO₂ mitigation, wastewater treatment, as biofertilizer or biostimulant in agriculture, particularly adding to the EU Bioeconomy strategy action plan.

Figure 1: Green microalgae appearances in the lab, photobioreactor and as biomass.

Figure 2: High-value compounds (HVC) produced in green microalgae. Percentages in this figure represent amount of particular HVC in *Chlorella*.

Within **GeneBEcon**, a **Horizon Europe-funded project** (grant number 101061015), the innovation potential of new genomic techniques (NGT) to enable a sustainable and zero-pollution bioeconomy in Europe is studied based on, among others, a case study in microalgae. NGT microalgae could open possibilities for a resource-efficient and clean production of industrially relevant compounds and the repurposing of microalgae residual biomass. **This technical report gives an overview of the possibilities of such a dual-purpose use of microalgae, i.e. as a production platform of HVCs, such**

as carotenoids, and using the residual biomass after HVC extraction, e.g. as animal feed. Within GeneBEcon an NGT toolbox is constructed for microalgae, and regulatory options are assessed in terms of their respective data requirements for risk assessment and the economic impact. Societal perceptions of NGT-derived products are also assessed. **Both the technical aspects and challenges as well as the legal and risk assessment issues are highlighted in this technical report.**

2. Microalgae production and use in the EU

2.1. Microalgae production in general

The diversity of commercially cultivated microalgae species is relatively low. More than 70% of the global market is dominated by just two species: *Chlorella* and *Spirulina*. Other notable, but less widely produced species include *Dunaliella salina* and *Haematococcus pluvialis*. Global sales revenues from microalgae are projected to reach \$3.8 billion by 2025. Of this total, \$1.4 billion is expected to come from the United States, \$1.0 billion from Europe, and \$0.9 billion from Asia. Within the Asian market, China accounts for approximately 40% of revenues, followed by Japan (23%) and India (15%), with a total annual *Spirulina* production estimated at around 3,000 tons and 2,000 tons per year for *Chlorella*.

Data on microalgae production in the EU are scattered and mainly based on estimations. A report from 2021 at the EU level showed a production of 182 tonnes dry weight (DW) of eukaryotic microalgae and 142 tonnes DW of *Limnospira* (also known as *Arthrospira* or 'spirulina') (Araujo *et al.*, 2021). However, these production levels might be outdated, as the **microalgal sector is growing very fast**, particularly during the last years.

To fill this gap, GeneBEcon has provided an overview of the microalgal sector in Europe ranked by country, cultivation system and microalgal strain. It was shown that the microalgal sector in Europe is focused on the high-value biomass (containing polysaccharides, lipids, proteins, pigments, phenolic compounds, minerals and vitamins), with applications in the food and/or feed industries, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals (Gallego *et al.*, 2025). **At least 66 microalgal companies based in Europe were identified that commercialize nearly 150 different microalgal-based products, and 49 companies providing biotech-related services.** Most of the enterprises manufacture more than two products, and at least five companies have several product lines, probably to maximise the use of algal biomass. France, Germany, The Netherlands and Spain are the European countries with a higher number of microalgal-producing enterprises. The cultivation system used in Europe depends on the microalgal strain and geographical location. Open raceway ponds and photobioreactors (PBR) are the preferred cultivation systems in southern Europe, whilst heterotrophic reactors (fermenters) are more common elsewhere (Gallego *et al.*, 2025). Interestingly, *Chlorella* spp., one of the most relevant microalgae produced in Europe, can be grown mixotrophic (both autotrophic and heterotrophic), whilst other microalgae are restricted to autotrophic growth.

2.2. Microalgae value chain

Currently, microalgae biomass is mainly directed to a single product value chain, in which one main valuable marketable product is obtained per production chain. However, the development of a multiproduct value chain (Figure 3), in which biomass valorization is enhanced by applying a cascade approach to obtain multiple valuable marketable products, opens huge possibilities to increase the economic value and to fully exploit the potential of microalgae. An interesting multiproduct value chain could be the extraction of HVCs, e.g., MAAs or carotenoids, and to repurpose the remaining biomass as an animal feed additive.

Figure 3: Overview of the possibilities to convert microalgae biomass into marketable biochemicals, bioactives, bioenergy, or other biomaterials in single product or multiproduct value chain.

The main strength of the microalgal sector in Europe is the use of cutting-edge biotechnologies and the available know-how supported by scientific research in universities and public institutions. By the end of 2024, the European Algal Biomass Association (EABA) had 80 scientific members (*i.e.*, research institutions), and 115 industrial members. There is a clear interest and an increasing trend in the incorporation of molecular tools in the cultivation and exploitation of microalgae. For example, at least **six companies are already working with NGT-derived microalgae in Europe**, either for carbon capture and utilization or to maximize the production of HVC (Gallego et al., 2025). Additionally, **several companies use residual effluents from other industries as a culture medium for microalgae**. None of the European microalgal producers has already incorporated both types of measures, *i.e.*, the use of gene-edited microalgal strains with increased yield of HVC in the production system, and valorization of the residual biomass after the main end-product is obtained.

By combining the optimal microalgal strain, optimal culture conditions and the use of metabolic engineering, a biomass with high content of HVCs could be obtained. This biomass could be implemented in a multiproduction value chain. Figure 4 shows the identification of (alternative) resources to achieve such circular economy approach in microalgae production systems, which would largely add to the measures from the EU Bioeconomy Action Plan.

Figure 4. Workflow of microalgae production following the conventional upstream cultivation (blue box) and downstream processing (yellow box). The circular bioeconomy approach (grey box) incorporates genetically improved strains to increase productivity and optimize resource use by incorporating alternative resources for microalgae cultivation (either renewable resources or sidestreams from the industrial activity), and valorization of the culture medium and residual biomass, once the main microalgal end-product is obtained. Two concrete measures were integrated (i.e., strain genetic improvement and use of residual microalgal biomass) to obtain products with potential applications in the food and feed sectors, agriculture and cosmetics (white boxes). Figure adapted from Gallego et al. (2025).

2.3. Microalgae as a production platform for carotenoids as high-value compounds

Because of their fast growth, stable production of biomass, and year-round cultivation, microalgae are an emerging production system for HVCs for chemical, pharmaceutical and other sectors. Among others, they are considered valuable producers of carotenoids, biosynthesized in their chloroplasts (Coleman et al. 2024). Compared to carotenoid production in plants, e.g. lutein production in Marigold, cultivation of microalgae for carotenoids could be done year-round, unlike seasonal plants, and requires no arable land and 2–10 times less water compared to marigold flowers. Moreover, microalgae have a growth rate that is 5-10 times faster than that of higher plants, which can significantly increase their carotenoid productivity (Coleman et al. 2024).

Carotenoids are a diverse group of naturally occurring pigments found in microalgae, playing essential roles in photosynthesis and cellular protection. These pigments, which include compounds such as β -carotene, astaxanthin, lutein, and zeaxanthin, contribute to light absorption and energy transfer while also serving as antioxidants that protect cells from oxidative stress. **Humans cannot synthesize carotenoids**

and must obtain them through their diet. Microalgae are considered one of the richest sources of carotenoids, with their production influenced by environmental factors such as light intensity, temperature, and nutrient availability. Due to their strong antioxidant properties and health benefits, carotenoids from microalgae have garnered significant interest for applications in nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals, cosmetics, and aquaculture (Table 1).

Table 1: Most important carotenoids, their producing microalgae, and health benefits and other applications (Adopted from Coleman et al. (2024)) (RE=retinol equivalent)

Carotenoid	Producing microalgae	Health benefits and other applications	Recommended dose
Astaxanthin	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i> , <i>Chlorococccum spp.</i> , <i>Chlorella zofigiensis</i>	Strong antioxidant property; anti-inflammatory effects; anti-cancer; cardiovascular health; aquaculture feed; nutraceutical	4-12mg/day
β-Carotene	<i>Dunaliella salina</i> , <i>Dunaliella bardawil</i> , <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Prevent night blindness; antioxidant property; prevents liver fibrosis; pro-vitamin A supplement; food and cosmetics	600 µg RE/day
Lutein	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Scenedesmus almeriensis</i> , <i>Muriellopsis spp.</i>	Prevents cataract and age-related macular degeneration; antioxidant property; anti-cancer; prevents cardiovascular diseases; food colorant	6 mg/day
Zeaxanthin	<i>Synechococcus spp.</i> , <i>Dunaliella salina</i> , <i>Nannochloropsis spp.</i>	Anti-cancer; anti-inflammatory; anti-allergy; against UV, skin redness; eye health; food and feed additive	2 mg/day
Fucoxanthin	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i> , <i>Isochrysis galbana</i> , <i>Odontella aurita</i>	Anti-obesity; antioxidant property; anti-inflammatory; cosmetic applications	1-6 mg/day
Violaxanthin	<i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i> , <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Nannochloropsis spp.</i>	Antioxidant; potential anti-cancer agent	Not established
Neoxanthin	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Dunaliella spp.</i>	Anti-inflammatory; antioxidant properties	Not established

The global carotenoid market is valued at 1.8 billion USD in 2021 and is projected to reach 2 billion USD by 2026 (Coleman et al. 2024), driven by increasing demand across various applications and the rising awareness of their health benefits. In the market for carotenoids there is a contrast between natural and synthetic, each with their market share dynamics. Chemical synthesis can be up to three times cheaper than natural sources. Consequently, natural carotenoids today only capture 10-20% of the market due to high production costs. However, this is changing as concerns about safety and environmental impact grow and the higher health benefits of natural carotenoids become more and more clear (Coleman et al. 2024). Another major reason for the preference towards natural carotenoids is their significant differences in forms and bioactivity compared to synthetic sources, with natural carotenoids showing complex mixtures of various isomers, and synthetic carotenoids typically occurring in a single esterified form. Further, Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents (NADES) are revolutionising carotenoid extraction through their green chemistry approach, offering enhanced solubility of carotenoids (up to 200 µg/mL compared to 107 µg/mL with n-

hexane), improved extraction efficiency, and reduced environmental impact, making them a sustainable alternative to conventional toxic organic solvents.

2.4. Microalgae biomass as animal feed additive

After extraction of HVC -within the concept of bio-circularity and zero-waste- the residual biomass could be further used, for example in animal feed. Microalgae could offer both nutritional benefits and health improvements, induced by the high amounts of nutritional compounds such as proteins and lipids, as well as bioactive compounds such as polyunsaturated fatty acids and antioxidants (including phenolics, flavonoids and carotenoids) (Murphy et al., 2023). By this, microalgae can be a sustainable alternative to the use of antibiotics (that have been forbidden for their prophylactic use in 2006) and to the now used fishmeal and soybean meal. Today soybean is a crucial protein source in poultry and livestock diets due to its high-quality protein composition. However, concerns related to soybean cultivation have increased in recent years, considering topics as global market dominance and sustainability challenges in production, such as monocropping and deforestation, leading to biodiversity loss (Amaral et al., 2021). Conventional crops are associated with environmental issues such as greenhouse gas emissions in the atmosphere and nitrogen emissions in the environment (Ahmad and Ashraf, 2023). Alternative protein sources with great potential are peas and other Leguminosae, cereals, insects and (micro)algae (Van Krimpen et al., 2013).

The bulk price of *Chlorella* and 'spirulina' currently ranges between €25 and €55 per kilogram, depending on production volumes, quality, production location and the production system used. After the extraction of HVCs, the remaining side streams can still hold significant value for other sectors, such as animal feed. However, the price of these side streams will depend on purity and the residual composition of the microalgae. For use in animal feed, additional costs will arise from meeting safety requirements. Furthermore, feed additives require EFSA authorization, which mandates proof of the functionality of a specific component.

Table 2: Overview of the potential benefits of microalgae biomass in animal feed

Animal	Potential benefits	Microalgae already used in research studies
Poultry (Laying Hens, Broilers)	Enhances egg yolk pigmentation (carotenoids); Improves growth performance and immune function; Increases omega-3 content in meat and eggs; improves intestinal morphology, antioxidant status and intestinal microbiome.	<i>Limnospira platensis</i> , <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i> (Khan et al. 2018 ; Hosseini-Vashan et al. 2020); <i>Scenedesmus</i> spp. (Olsen et al. 2021)
Swine (Pigs)	Boosts immune response (antioxidants, vitamins); Improves gut health (prebiotic effects); Enhances meat quality (higher omega-3 content)	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i> , <i>Nannochloropsis</i> spp. (Lum et al. 2013; Hwang et al. 2020)
Ruminants (Cows, Sheep, Goats)	Increases milk yield and improves milk omega-3 content; Enhances rumen fermentation (better fiber digestion); Strengthens immune function	<i>Schizochytrium</i> spp., <i>Chlorella</i> spp. (Schwarm et

Animal	Potential benefits	Microalgae already used in research studies
		al. 2016; de Souza et al. 2021)
Aquaculture (Fish, Shrimp)	Enhances pigmentation (astaxanthin, canthaxanthin); Improves growth and survival rates; Replaces fishmeal as a sustainable protein source	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i> , <i>Nannochloropsis</i> spp., <i>Tetraselmis</i> spp. (Shah et al. 2018; Camacho-Rodriguez et al. 2020)

2.5. Outstanding challenges for the dual-purpose use of microalgae in a circular and zero-waste bioeconomy

The transition towards a new bioeconomy model, as proposed by the EU Bioeconomy Strategy, aims to strengthen and scale-up the bio-based sectors, with measures such as the minimization of waste generation and the maximisation of the resource value (EC, 2018). In microalgal production systems, adopting these principles will not only contribute to a circular bioeconomy model, but also to the economic feasibility of the production (Gallego *et al.*, 2025). However, there are several outstanding challenges that are needed to be addressed to enable more efficiency and feasible costs.

1. The **production of microalgae needs to be upscaled**. For this it is needed to fully understand the growth kinetics and to optimise production parameters accordingly. In addition, most HVC extraction methods involve solvents like acetone or ethanol. These solvents can degrade the nutritional quality of the remaining biomass. Therefore, it is needed to **develop mild, food-grade, or green extraction methods**, such as enzyme-assisted or ultrasound-assisted extraction, and optimised biorefinery processes to retain the protein and amino acid integrity.

Scaling up microalgae production enables sustainable biomass production to be used in a circular bioeconomy. Microalgae bioprocess offers important environmental advantages, including reduced land and water requirements while capturing CO₂ during cultivation, supporting European Green Deal objectives while creating new economic opportunities in the bioeconomy sector.

2. Despite the high interest in HVC from microalgae in general, and natural carotenoids in particular, **high culture costs and sometimes low HVC yields** are bottlenecks for their commercialisation. **Advanced cultivation conditions and metabolic engineering might offer solutions** to enhance the HVC production in microalgae. For this, more research is essential to evaluate the possibilities of metabolic engineering through gene editing and altered cultivation conditions.
3. Some microalgae species, e.g., *Chlorella vulgaris*, have **thick cell walls**, making their nutrients less bioavailable for humans and animals and decreasing their digestibility. Mechanical or enzymatic **cell wall disruption** can be used to enhance digestibility, and fermentation or hydrolysis of the biomass can be performed to improve nutrient absorption. In addition, it is essential to use the **correct formulation and inclusion rate** of the microalgae biomass in the animal feed. This also varies depending on microalgae species and processing methods used.

- To make dual-purpose microalgae biorefineries less competitive with traditional feed ingredients (e.g. soybean meal, fishmeal), it is crucial to **develop cost-effective large-scale cultivation methods** and/or to integrate circular economy models by coupling with waste CO₂ capture or agriculture waste nutrient recycling. **Regulations on feed and food safety and novel ingredients** can slow down this process. Food, feed, clinical and toxicological trials are needed to generate safety data for regulatory approval and consumer education on the benefits of microalgae-derived products is essential. In addition, if metabolic engineering is successful to enhance the production of HVC in microalgae, the **EU legislation for use of NGT microalgae** may hamper applications, as these are considered as Genetically modified organisms (GMO) for which a very detailed and costly risk assessment is needed preceding market introduction.

The GeneBEcon project tackled all these challenges as is described in the following sections.

3. Scaling up the production of microalgae

3.1. Key principles for successful upscaling

To fully exploit the potential of microalgae, its production needs to be scaled up. Hence, a good understanding of the growth kinetics, potential challenges, and production parameters is crucial.

Within GeneBEcon, upscaling experiments showed that **a gradual volume increase is essential**, involving a stepwise approach from small tissue culture flasks (20-40 mL) to small photobioreactors (0.5-5 L) and finally to larger tubular photobioreactors (25-250 L) (Figure 5). This gradual expansion allowed microalgae cultures to acclimatize to new conditions while maintaining adequate cell density, thereby avoiding stress and prolonged lag phases in growth cycles.

Also, the **photobioreactor design** represented a critical factor for successful upscaling. Most commonly, tubular photobioreactors are used with horizontal transparent acrylic tubes arranged in a rectangular helix, equipped with an air-lift circulation system for mixing and degassing, and LED illumination with adjustable intensity based on culture density. These systems also incorporate integrated sensors for pH, oxygen, and temperature monitoring, along with a CO₂ injection system for pH control and carbon supply. This comprehensive design ensures efficient light distribution, proper gas exchange, and effective removal of excess oxygen produced during photosynthesis, which could otherwise inhibit growth.

In addition, it was clear that maintaining **optimal cultivation conditions is crucial to maximize productivity**. Different microalgae species require different cultivation conditions. For example, for *Chlorella* species optimal conditions included precise temperature control ($20.5 \pm 1.4^\circ\text{C}$), pH regulation (7.84 ± 0.12) through automated CO₂ injection, and light intensity management ($85\text{-}588 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) that adjusts with increasing cell density.

In general, implementing a consistent day/night cycle and regularly supplementing the culture with nutrients, trace metals, and vitamins ensured continuous growth and prevented limitation-induced stress responses in the microalgae population.

Figure 5 Gradual volume increase for the upscaling of microalgae cultivation

3.2. Challenges and considerations related to upscaling of microalgae cultivation

Several significant challenges emerged during microalgae upscaling. **Biofouling (i.e., the accumulation of microalgae on the surface of the bioreactor) management** became essential as microalgae adhered to the photobioreactor surfaces, reducing suspended biomass and light penetration. Strategies such as increased water flow velocity, short-term pH increase, etc. require further investigation to mitigate this issue. **Growth rate optimization** presented another challenge. For example, the wild-type *Chlorella* sp. OLI 26 SB grows relatively slowly compared to other commercial strains, possibly due to its long-term laboratory cultivation since 1994. Finally, **regulatory compliance** adds complexity when cultivating genetically modified or NGT strains, requiring adherence to EU directives, implementation of containment measures, proper waste disposal protocols, and dedicated equipment usage (see section 6). Addressing these challenges is essential for efficient and compliant large-scale microalgae production.

4. Increasing carotenoid production in microalgae

Despite their potential, the natural yields of carotenoids from microalgae are often too low to efficiently meet industrial demands. Additionally, cultivation costs, including those for light, nutrients, and harvesting, can be prohibitively high, limiting large-scale commercial viability. Stress conditions such as high light exposure, nutrient starvation, and salinity can enhance carotenoid accumulation, but they often come at the cost of reduced biomass productivity (Ren

Figure 6: Cultivation strategies and gene editing can be used to increase carotenoid production.

et al. (2021)). To overcome these limitations, advanced cultivation and gene-editing techniques are evaluated in GeneBEcon to optimize carotenoid biosynthesis and improve overall yields (Figure 6).

4.1. Cultivation techniques to increase carotenoid production

The optimal parameters for maximising the carotenoid content can reduce the biomass productivity (g DW/L/day), thereby lowering the overall carotenoid productivity (mg/g DW). Therefore, a balanced approach is necessary to optimise both carotenoid content and biomass productivity and this is examined in GeneBEcon (Figure 7).

Figure 7: *Chlorella vulgaris* grown under different growth conditions. From left to right: (1) BG-11 medium + glucose + DO10%, (2) Basal glucose medium + glucose + DO50%, (3) BG-11 medium + glucose + DO50%, (4) BG-11 medium + glucose + NaCl + DO50%. DO=dissolved oxygen; BG-11 is the standard medium to grow *Chlorella*.

Awaiting results from GeneBEcon, to show the potential of advanced cultivation methods in the production on HVC, here a literature example is given for lutein production in *Chlorella*. The most effective cultivation strategy, yielding a good lutein productivity, involves cultivating *Chlorella sorokiniana* FZU60 under heterotrophic conditions in fed-batch mode with 3-fold concentrated Mann and Myer's medium supplemented with glucose and urea, while controlling dissolved oxygen in the fermenter (Xie et al. 2022). This approach achieves a lutein concentration of 415.93 mg/L (= 2.57 mg/g DW) due to high biomass concentration in the fermenter. Controlling operational parameters such as pH, ensuring effective gas supply (ambient air and CO₂), and maintaining dissolved oxygen (DO) levels in the fermenter are crucial for achieving higher biomass production and consequently enhancing lutein productivity. To enhance the lutein content, two-stage strategies can be employed. Using fed-batch heterotrophic conditions followed by mixotrophic conditions for *C. sorokiniana* MB-1-M12 results in a lutein content of 8.19 mg/g DW after 14 days of cultivation (Chen et al. 2022). The fed-batch mixotrophy followed by mixotrophic conditions for *C. sorokiniana* FZU60 achieves a lutein content of 11.22 mg/g DW after 8 days of cultivation (Ma et al. (2020). Although, a single-stage process might be easier to operate compared to a two-way strategy, it is clear that the lutein content is higher in a two-way strategy compared to only heterotrophic conditions, which might be important for further downstream processing.

Important to note, energy consumption for artificial lighting under mixotrophic and phototrophic conditions can significantly increase the production cost of microalgae, which is not the case for heterotrophic cultivation. Apart from the energy costs associated with lighting, mixotrophic and phototrophic conditions can reduce the ecological footprint by lowering CO₂ emissions, thanks to their carbon sequestration capabilities, which is not the case for heterotrophic cultivation. Scalability of the used strategy is also important for commercialization and reducing production costs of microalgae.

Under heterotrophic and mixotrophic conditions, both microalgae and bacteria compete for organic carbon, with bacteria often outnumbering microalgae due to their shorter doubling times. As a result, keeping anoxic conditions through the scaling process is important to avoid culture crashes or contamination issues, which could raise safety concerns for human consumption. Selecting carotenoid-producing species that can resist extreme environments, such as low-pH and high-salt conditions, might offer a solution for contamination during cultivation. These resilient species could enhance the stability and efficiency of large-scale carotenoid production systems.

4.2. Gene-editing to increase carotenoid production

Gene editing technologies, particularly CRISPR/Cas, offer powerful tools to enhance carotenoid production in microalgae by precisely modifying genes involved in metabolic pathways. By targeting key regulatory genes, carotenoid biosynthesis can be optimised, yield increased, and commercial viability improved.

In GeneBEcon, a systematic approach is used to apply gene editing, starting with species or strain selection and target identification, followed by the choice of transformation technique and mutation screening. The developed **GeneBEwise website** (<https://genebewise.genebecon.eu/>), serves as a valuable resource to guide researchers through these steps, providing insights applicable to various gene-editing applications in different organisms.

For species selection, several microalgal species were considered. *Chlorella* is recognized for its naturally lutein production, making it an attractive candidate for increasing its lutein concentration (Wu et al. (2024)). However, gene-editing in *Chlorella* is relatively new, and successful transformation remains a challenge. *Nannochloropsis* is well known for its well-established gene-editing techniques, and, although not primarily associated with the production of a specific carotenoid, it produces e.g. zeaxanthin and violaxanthin (Table 1) (Wang et al. 2016; Naduthodi et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2022). Within GeneBEcon, initial transformation attempts in *Chlorella* were unsuccessful due to its rigid cell wall, while ***Nannochloropsis* transformation was successful**, as confirmed by antibiotic selection and PCR on colony-forming units (CFUs) with primers designed to amplify part of the plasmid (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Successful transformation in *Nannochloropsis*

Target selection for gene-editing is based on a **detailed analysis of the carotenoid biosynthesis pathway** (Figure 9). Aiming to increase the zeaxanthin content, gene editing could focus on targeting *zeaxanthin epoxidase* (*ZEP1* and *ZEP2*), preventing the conversion of zeaxanthin into antheraxanthin. Additionally, *violaxanthin deoxidase* (*VDE*) and *violaxanthin deoxidase-like* (*VDL*) are interesting target genes allowing to block the conversion of violaxanthin back to zeaxanthin and its conversion into neoxanthin, aiming to increase violaxanthin levels.

Figure 9: Biosynthesis pathway of carotenoids

In GeneBEcon, transformations are performed to target these four genes, aiming for knockouts of the *ZEP* genes potentially leading to increased zeaxanthin levels, and knockouts of *VDE* and/or *VDL* genes that would result in higher violaxanthin production. For each target gene, two gRNAs were designed, considering target specificity and on-target activity. Several electroporations were carried out, resulting in 2 confirmed mutants for the *VDL* gene (Figure 10). The CRISPR-induced mutations included the insertion of one nucleotide (T) and two nucleotides (TT), both leading to a frameshift and a premature stop codon.

Both mutants are therefore strong candidates for a successful *VDL* gene knock-out and will be further cultivated for carotenoid content analysis.

Figure 10: Chromatogram obtained after Sanger sequencing of WT and two colony forming units (CFUs) that appeared following *Nannochloropsis* transfection with a CRISPR plasmid targeting the *VDL* gene. CRISPR-induced mutations were detected in both CFUs, located four nucleotides downstream of the PAM sequence.

5. Using microalgae residual biomass as poultry feed

After extraction of the carotenoids, the **residual biomass** could be further used, for example, in poultry feed. Broilers are the most produced and consumed terrestrial animals worldwide (OECD-FAO, 2021) with high production and protein conversion efficiency. But the increased pressure on its production, i.e., increased average daily gain and shortened lifespan, has led to health problems in broilers. Antibiotic growth promoters have been used in the poultry industry since the 1940s, improving animal performance and health status. However, the prophylactic use of these antibiotics, i.e., the preventive use as growth promoter, was banned in 2006 due to regulatory restrictions (EC, 2003). New feed additives such as pre- and probiotics and enzymes are required to maintain production levels and avoid health problems in feedstock (Dibner & Richards, 2005). Currently, antibiotics are replaced by the use of organic acids (such as carboxylic acids and short chain fatty acids, available as salts), probiotic microorganisms (e.g., *Lactobacillus* and *Streptococcus*), prebiotic substrates (such as gluco-, fructo- and mannan-oligosaccharides), vitamins, minerals, plant extracts, phytobiotics (e.g., phenols, flavonoids, tannins and saponins) and antimicrobial peptides (Yadav et al., 2016).

Microalgae, rich in bioactive compounds with many potential beneficial properties, could offer a promising alternative to replace antibiotics in poultry feed formulations, as is evaluated in the GeneBEcon project (Figure 11). Furthermore, due to the high protein content, e.g. in *Chlorella vulgaris*, it could also serve as a protein source, (partially) replacing soybean.

The use of residual microalgal biomass could have a dual purpose in poultry feed: firstly, for its health-promoting effects as **feed additive** and secondly, for its high **protein content**.

Figure 11: The work scheme by which in GeneBEcon the potential of the use of residual microalgal biomass as poultry feed additive and protein source is assessed.

A first step to assess the benefits of microalgae in poultry feed is determining whether algae need processing to break their sometimes rigid cell wall (as is e.g. the case in *Chlorella*) (Safi et al., 2014). Possible processing techniques are freezing, freeze-drying, (cold-)pasteurization, pulsed electric field (PEF), high pressure homogenization, bead milling, ultrasonication, microwave radiation and enzymatic disruption in order to increase the availability and digestibility of nutrients (Postma et al., 2016). PEF is a non-thermal technique, mainly used in the food industry for preservation of food due to its microbial inactivation capacity (Jeyamkondan et al., 1999).

The potential of **microalgal biomass as feed additive** was investigated. It was shown that a PEF treatment had a high cell disruption efficiency, up to 80%, both for autotrophic and heterotrophic *C. vulgaris*. This **cell disruption was essential to guarantee a good digestibility** of the feed. Feeds with PEF-processed *C. vulgaris* had no significant difference in digestibility of crude protein, fat and ash compared to feeds without *Chlorella*, showing **that including low dosages (up to 2%) of *C. vulgaris* in broiler feed does not compromise its digestibility**. But the inclusion of 2% *C. vulgaris* in broiler diets showed **no or only a minimal impact**, compared to the control group, **on overall performance, health, and meat quality**:

- No significant effects on feed intake, daily gain and feed conversion ratio;
- Some improvements in litter quality and footpad condition when fed heterotrophic algae;

- More gut leakage (based on ovotransferrin concentrations, a marker for gut leakage) but increased the antioxidant capacity in the blood;
- No significant differences in intestinal morphology (Figure 12A);
- Darker, more intense red, and more yellow breast meat (likely due to pigment uptake) (Figure 12B);
- More abnormalities such as wooden breast and white striping.

Figure 12: (A) Microscopic image of a hematoxylin and eosin staining of a morpho-histological section of the duodenum of broilers. Villus height, crypt depth and thickness of the tunica muscularis are indicated. (B) Breast meat of a broiler chicken fed with a control feed (upper) and fed with 2% *C. vulgaris* (below).

Overall, while *C. vulgaris* supplementation had some minor effects on specific welfare and meat quality parameters, its impact on performance was negligible, and it did not significantly affect the health of the broilers. Therefore, inclusion of residual biomass in low amounts is possible in poultry feed.

Increasing levels of *C. vulgaris* inclusion in broiler feeds (up to 20%), aiming for its use as protein source, negatively impact the digestibility of crude protein, crude fat, gross energy, and crude ash. Limiting *C. vulgaris* inclusion to no more than 10% of the broiler diet is highly recommended to avoid substantial decreases in nutrient digestibility. However, even at 10% inclusion, feed digestibility is already significantly lower compared to a control feed with soybean meal. While *C. vulgaris* presents a promising sustainable alternative protein source, its application in broiler diets is currently constrained by digestibility issues at higher inclusion levels, most likely due to the rigid cell wall. Continued exploration of cell processing techniques and formulation strategies is essential to fully discover the potential of microalgae as a protein source in animal feed.

6. EU regulations related to the use of microalgae

As microalgae have a variety of uses, ranging from food supplements (Gallego et al. 2025), animal feed (Van Nerom et al. 2024a; Van Nerom et al. 2024b; Van Nerom et al. 2025) to biofertilizers (Dagnaisser et al. 2022) and pharmaceutical applications (Huang et al. 2024), also the regulatory landscape in the EU is complex and fragmented, creating challenges for e.g. producers seeking market approval (Gallego et al. 2025). Depending on their use, different regulatory frameworks apply. The most important differentiation is between the **classification “genetically modified or not”** and **“novel food or not”**. The EU Blue Economy Strategy (2021) further highlights the potential of algae, including microalgae, as a key resource for a sustainable and circular bioeconomy, further underlining the need for a coherent and innovation-friendly regulatory framework.

EU regulates the handling and use of GMO through various legal acts. First, if genetically modified microorganisms (GMMs) are to be used in contained systems such as laboratories or bioreactors, Directive 2009/41/EC applies with its provisions that mitigate risks to human health and the environment. GMO microalgae cultivated in open systems like ponds on the other hand require a more comprehensive assessment, as set out in Directive 2001/18/EC which applies to the deliberate release of GMOs into the environment. Secondly, food and feed containing or consisting of GMOs or produced from GMOs are known as genetically modified food and feed. Independent of the contained or open production system, regulation No 1829/2003/EC, along with the implementing regulation No 503/2013, applies when a food or feed product is intended to be placed on the market, and the products must undergo a comprehensive risk assessment for food and feed safety (see section 7).

NGTs like CRISPR/Cas have the potential to expand the application of microalgae (Rumin et al. 2021), but regulatory uncertainty persists (Wessler et al. 2023) regarding their environmental impact assessments (Gallego et al. 2025; EFSA Scientific Committee 2020). The debate on NGTs at EU level is well underway, as the Council of the EU, the European Parliament and the European Commission now enter the next round of discussions on the new NGT regulation proposal, in form of a Trilogue (Purnhagen et al. 2023). While the proposed regulation focuses on plants obtained by NGTs, the differentiated approach might set a precedent for a future regulation of microalgae and microorganisms in general. Recent findings by Mullins et al. (2024) indicate that while no novel hazards were identified for NGT microorganisms compared to those obtained through established genomic techniques or conventional mutagenesis, existing EFSA guidance documents are either partially or even not applicable for the assessment of NGT-derived microalgae. Future regulatory framework could adopt, for example, a strain- or product-based risk assessment approach and further ensure an updated, tailored guidance document for microbial and algal applications.

In case a new microalgae product is intended for human consumption and insofar as Regulation No 1829/2003/EC on GM food and feed is not applicable, the Novel Food Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 applies since novel microalgae strains will most likely fall within its scope. It is the main regulatory framework for innovative food products and covers foods which were not consumed to a significant degree within the European Union before 1997. Some microalgae, such as certain *Chlorella* and *Spirulina* species already have a history of consumption in EU and are therefore not considered novel foods (Cruz and Vasconcelos 2024; Reinhardt and Monaco, 2025).

Microalgae can also be used as animal feed, as is already the case for *Limnospira platensis* (also known as *Arthrospira platensis* or ‘spirulina’) and *L. maxima* (also known as *Arthrospira maxima*) which are not considered novel food and are registered as animal feed or ingredients for animal feed under the Feed Regulation No. 767/2009/EC which applies to their use in animal nutrition (Gallego et al. 2025).

In GeneBEcon a closed-loop system is developed where microalgae, a.o. *Chlorella vulgaris*, are cultivated for the high-value carotenoids, while the sidestream biomass is repurposed as a poultry feed additive (Van Nerom et al. 2024a; Van Nerom et al. 2024b; Van Nerom et al. 2025), creating a more sustainable poultry diet and supporting the circular economy by maximizing resource efficiency and minimizing waste. This case study illustrates how different regulatory frameworks apply to the same starting material. Depending on the intended use of the carotenoids, different regulatory frameworks apply. For example, if lutein is intended as a colouring agent, it is already approved under the Food Additives Regulation (Regulation No. 1333/2008/EC) to be marketed as such. The sidestream biomass used for animal feed falls under both the Regulation No. 767/2009/EC on the placing on the market and use of feed and the Regulation No 1829/2003/EC on genetically modified food and feed.

7. Biosafety requirements to ensure the safety of a gene-edited microalgae

7.1. Biosafety requirements to ensure safe use of NGT microalgae in lab conditions

As of today, the safe use of NGT microalgae in laboratory and pilot-scale production environments requires comprehensive biosafety protocols and strict adherence to the regulatory framework (EU regulations for handling NGT organisms under Directives 2009/41/EC or 2001/18/EC). Within GeneBEcon, standard operating procedures (SOP) have been developed for working with NGT microalgae to implement several critical elements to ensure containment and prevent accidental environmental release. Proper containment includes utilizing closed-system cultivation in PBRs fitted with one-way air filters to prevent aerosol release. For smaller cultures, additional containment measures include transporting samples in capped centrifuge tubes placed inside sealed plastic bags when moving between laboratory spaces. All cultivation equipment must be clearly labeled with strain identification, date, handler's initials, and GMO classification. Also, thermal inactivation of the biomass provides a critical biosafety control point in the processing workflow. Harvested biomass is transferred to sealed, heat-resistant containers and subjected to standardized heat treatment (75°C for 20 minutes), with temperature monitoring at the geometric center to ensure complete inactivation of all GMO or NGT cells before allowing the material to leave containment facilities for subsequent extraction processes. Furthermore, decontamination protocols include specific procedures for different waste streams. Liquid waste (spent medium) must be neutralized with 0.5% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for at least one hour before disposal, while solid waste must be collected in designated yellow biohazard bags for certified disposal. All reusable equipment requires thorough autoclaving before subsequent use, and immediate decontamination with 70% ethanol is mandatory for any accidental spills.

Risk management extends to personnel practices, requiring laboratory staff to wear appropriate personal protective equipment including laboratory coats and nitrile gloves when handling GMO cultures. Detailed documentation in logbooks tracking all culture transfers, growth parameters, and waste disposal activities provides critical traceability. For larger-scale operations using 250 L photobioreactors, additional safety measures include spill containment trays with sensors, CO₂ monitoring systems, and emergency shutdown procedures (Figure 13).

Figure 13 Pilot-scale laboratory for the cultivation and processing of NGT microalgae

7.2. Biosafety requirements to ensure safety of NGT microalgae in the value chain

The risk assessment of a GMO, including as of today NGT microalgae, aims to determine their potential adverse impact relative to its conventional counterpart. The assessment of its comparative safety involves generating data by collecting and assessing available information. The depth and scope of biosafety data necessary to verify this comparative safety is defined by regulatory legislation. Under the current legislation, Directive 2001/18/EC and Regulation No 1829/2003/EC, a full risk assessment of the microalgae would need to be performed as specified by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA). This includes not only thorough characterization of molecular and phenotypical characteristics, but also e.g. mandatory data collection. In this context, EFSA guidance documents are currently being updated—for instance, the *Draft guidance on the characterisation and risk assessment of microorganisms used in the food chain* reflects an effort to ensure more tailored and coherent evaluation of microorganisms, including those modified with NGTs.

EFSA and the EC are convinced that the current regulation is not fit for purpose and less biosafety data requirements are adequate for the safety assessment of certain NGT-derived (higher) plants. However, it is not yet determined when these discussions will also impact microalgae in the future. Within GeneBEcon **six regulatory options** are defined and investigated (including the current GMO regulation, i.e., the status quo or Option 1) for NGT-derived plants and microalgae. The extent to which an applicant has to provide data for regulatory risk assessment (RA) varies for the different options¹. A basic requirement independent of all options are **verification data**, that enable the applicant and the Competent Authority (CA) to conclude on the trigger for regulatory assessment. These verification data include a general description of the trait and the molecular characterisation of the derived microalgae.

Depending on the regulatory option and the pre-assessment of the verification data by the CA, **further biosafety data** are required for the approval process. These data must be provided by an applicant to a CA for a comprehensive risk assessment according to the regulatory options. Those options are outlined here in brief (Figure 14) and were published by Purnhagen et al. (2023)

¹ See: https://genebecon.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/D1.1_V9.pdf

Figure 14: Six different regulatory options as determined within GeneBEcon. For each regulatory option the risk assessment procedure is schematically overviewed.

The regulation of microalgae also depends on the cultivation system. Laboratory and small-scale cultivation of microalgae is mostly done in labs or greenhouses in a contained system (see 7.1), therefore falling under the regulation of the Directive 2009/41/EC. For large scale microalgae production open, or semi open systems, like ponds, are used. Such cultivation systems require a more comprehensive assessment and would fall under control of the Directive 2001/18/EC or, in future, under control of one of the six alternative regulatory options.

The **cost estimates for biosafety requirements** are highly variable, depending on the regulatory option. Major drivers are:

- Hardware-related (e.g., technical machinery for sequencing or High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry);
- Human resources (e.g. wages and experience),
- NGT application specific (e.g. data availability during own product development or licensing)
- Microalgae production and environmental exposure.

To calculate the costs, the need for resources in the form of “monetary costs” was discussed and estimated with researchers in GeneBEcon developing NGT-microalgae, taking into account ‘best case’ genotype development². In addition, also literature research was done to determine and estimate costs and to define the frame of necessary resources³. Ten samples (showing 10 genotypes) are assumed for each application. For the following list of required biosafety data and the associated costs, it is assumed that the genetic modification of the NGT microalgae meets the most optimal approval criteria for each regulatory option and thus represents the lowest data requirements for each case. In all cases NGT microalgae regulated under Option 1-6 do not require plant variety testing and registration if listed for cultivation in the EU.

As the developmental steps and the collection of verification data is done fully in a contained use setting, no environmental risk assessment on microalgae has to be done for this step. Biosafety data generated from contained systems can be used for the authorisation of NGT microalgae production in an open system, e.g. for comparative risk analysis, feed assessments and environmental risk assessment. The full set of biosafety data would be only required in Option 1, since NGT microalgae would then fall under the same regulatory requirements as classical GMO. A similar set of biosafety data would be needed for Option 2, which only allows the reduction of some feed assessment studies like rodent feeding trails. In Option 3 and Option 5 no biosafety data would be required, if the validation data confirm the absence of foreign DNA. The Options 4 and 6 would require at least some feeding studies and a comparative analysis, based on the risk estimated from the pheno- and genotype. Environmental RA is not needed for these two options.

² The modifications in the NGT microalgae aim to increase the high-value compounds, carotenoids, in the microalgae. Information on the candidate genes and gene families by phylogenetic analysis, including blast searches, protein alignments, phylogenetic trees, etc., is part of the verification data collection and is required as pre-assessment data for every regulatory option. Genome diversity (e.g. SNPs) and allelic variants is characterized in the experimental material used for CRISPR and is taken into account for sgRNA and primer design. The sgRNAs used for editing of candidate genes are designed via screening all available genomic information (WGS data and assemblies) of experimental microalgae strains and of the target genes with bioinformatics tools (e.g. SMAP design pipeline, FlashFry, CRISPOR), which includes a putative off-target search. The induced DNA breaks will be repaired by non-homologous end joining (NHEJ) without using DRTs, leading to mutations in the gene or the promotor region of the gene to enhance accumulation of carotenoids. Electroporation was used as transfection method. Both, plasmids and RNPs, are used as delivery vehicles. Cas9 protein can be purchased from a commercial provider (e.g. IDT: <https://eu.idtdna.com/pages>) and is free of DNA contaminations. In case transient Cas9 expression is achieved using plasmid DNA, the absence of integrated delivery vector DNA is confirmed by WGS Illumina sequencing or related NGS techniques. To validate the success of the approach, HiPlex Amplicon sequencing will be used to identify the mutant allele at DNA sequence level and High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) to measure the concentration of the high-value compounds in comparison with the concentration in a wild type strain.

³ See: https://genebecon.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/09/D1.1_V9.pdf

Verification data requirements range from T€ 2.6 - T€ 9.8 for verification of the “conventional-like” character and from T€ 7.1 - T€ 25.2 for data to identify potential risks of a “non-conventional-like” microalgae under Option 3 (Figure 15). In Option 4, for verification as novel, the costs of data collection range between T€ 4.8 - T€ 12.2. The costs for verification data in Option 5, proving the absence of foreign DNA, range between T€ 1.4 - T€ 6.1. The verification costs in Option 6 range from T€ 5.1 to T€ 8.0 (Figure 15). After the verification step, further regulatory needs for a case-specific RA triggers the delivery of biosafety data. The costs for further biosafety data range from M€ 2.314 - M€ 16.022 (Option 3 if the microalgae is not conventional-like and not “as safe as conventional microalgae” or Option 5, if foreign DNA is present), M€ 1,827 - M€ 8.520 (Option 4 if the trait is novel), and M€ 1.628 - M€ 8.022 (Option 6 if the trait is classified as high hazard) (Figure 15). The verification costs alone are relatively low when compared to the cost of the RA under Option 2 with M€ 2.314 – M€ 16.023 and, in particular, the status quo (Option 1) with M€ 4.828 – M€ 16.022 which is similar to the estimated costs by the EU Commission ranging from M€ 5.460 - M€ 18.560

Figure 15 Estimated costs for NGT microalgae biosafety data according to the six regulatory options examined in the GeneBEcon project. Option 2 & 3 correspond to Category 1 and 2 NGT regulatory proposal [for higher plants] of the EU Commission

Overall, independent of the regulatory option, verification data are required for decisions on the regulatory classification (Figure 14). Additional biosafety data are dependent on the geno- or phenotype of the NGT microalgae and the regulatory trigger. In case of conventional-like NGT microalgae, options 3 and 5 are the options with the best cost-effectiveness (Figure 15). The Legal Status Quo and Status Quo-like Options 1 and 2 require the full, or almost full set of biosafety data, and are therefore associated with the most expensive authorisation process (Figure 15). Options 4 and 6 are intermediate cost-effective (Figure 15).

8. Conclusions

Microalgae have significant potential in biotechnology, environmental sustainability, and the broader bioeconomy. As microalgae cultivation does not compete for arable land and can thrive in various environments, including wastewater and saline conditions, they also have a significant role in circular economy models, where waste streams can be repurposed to support their growth. In a world facing pressing challenges such as climate change, food insecurity, and energy shortages, microalgae emerge as a promising solution due to their high-value biochemical composition, rapid growth rates, year-round cultivation, and capacity for carbon capture. Their versatility allows them to be utilized in diverse industries, including food and feed production, biofuel generation, pharmaceuticals, and wastewater treatment.

However, despite their numerous advantages, the large-scale commercialisation of microalgae-based products remains hindered by several challenges. High production costs, and technological constraints in optimising yields may limit their economic feasibility. Furthermore, regulatory hurdles present additional barriers that must be overcome to unlock their full potential. In the GeneBEcon project, several of these challenges were addressed with a multidisciplinary and international consortium of researchers and stakeholders.

Successful scaling up of microalgae production requires systematic approaches to volume expansion, careful reactor design, and precise control of cultivation parameters. Furthermore, it was shown that metabolic engineering by applying CRISPR/Cas targeting the carotenoid biosynthesis pathway, combined with optimized culture conditions, could pave the way for a more viable and scalable production system for carotenoids from microalgae. The experience gained from cultivating wild-type *Chlorella* and scaling up its production provided valuable insights for future work with NGT strains. In addition, despite the current challenge of energy-intensive downstream processing in microalgae, also advancements in extraction and purification technologies are made, holding promise for overcoming these hurdles. The metabolic engineering strategy developed within GeneBEcon is not limited to carotenoid biosynthesis but can be applied to enhance other high-value compounds in microalgae, fully unlocking their biotechnological potential in the future.

An illustrative example of a dual-purpose use of microalgae is shown in GeneBEcon by producing HVCs while maintaining a zero-waste approach through the utilization of residual biomass for poultry feed applications. Feeding trials performed so far conclude that *Chlorella vulgaris* has potential as protein source, however inclusion levels under 10% are highly recommended and further processing and formulation techniques must be investigated. Research is still ongoing to investigate *C. vulgaris*' potential as a feed additive. At the moment it can be shown that low dosages do not seem to have a significant negative impact on performance or health, indicating that inclusion of residual biomass in low amounts is possible in poultry feed.

Successful integration of dual-purpose use of microalgae into mainstream industries will require sustained efforts in innovation, cost reduction, and regulatory support. GeneBEcon showed that a set of diverse legal acts and guidance need to be considered, and that the regulatory framework is complex and fragmented. Related to the use of NGT microalgae, independent of the regulatory option, verification data are always required for decisions on the regulatory classification. Additional biosafety data are dependent on the geno- or phenotype of the NGT microalgae and the regulatory trigger. In case of conventional-like NGT microalgae, proposed options 3 and 5 are the options with the best cost-effectiveness. The Legal Status Quo and Status Quo-like Options 1 and 2 require the full, or almost full set of biosafety data, and are therefore associated with the most expensive authorisation process. Options 4 and 6 are intermediate cost-effective.

In conclusion, microalgae offer a compelling and viable solution to many contemporary global challenges. By leveraging their unique properties and addressing existing limitations, microalgae have the potential to significantly contribute to a more sustainable, resource-efficient, zero-waste, and environmentally friendly future. In GeneBEcon, their potential for a dual-purpose use, and hence significant contribution to a circular bioeconomy, was nicely shown by developing a strategy to increase their production of high-value compounds and repurposing the residual biomass after extraction as poultry feed additive.

References

- Ahmad A, Ashraf SS. Sustainable food and feed sources from microalgae: Food security and the circular bioeconomy. *Algal Res* 2023;74:103185. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.algal.2023.103185>.
- Amaral DF, de Souza Ferreira Filho JB, Chagas ALS, Adami M. Expansion of soybean farming into deforested areas in the amazon biome: the role and impact of the soy moratorium. *Sustain Sci* 2021;16:1295–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00942-x>.
- Araújo R, Vazquez Calderon F., Sanchez Lopez J, Costa Azevedo I, Bruhn A, Fluch S, Garcia Tasende M et al. (2021) Current status of the algae production industry in Europe: an emerging sector of the blue bioeconomy. *Front Mar Sci* 7, 626389
- Camacho-Rodríguez J, González-López CV, Cerón-García MC, Molina-Grima E (2020) Microalgae as a source of natural pigments for aquaculture. *Reviews in Aquaculture* 12(3), 1791–1810
- Chen JH, Nagarajan D, Huang Y, Zhu X, Liao Q, Chang JS (2022) A Novel and Effective Two-Stage Cultivation Strategy for Enhanced Lutein Production with *Chlorella Sorokiniana*. *Biochem. Eng. J.* 188, 108688
- Coleman B, Vereecke E, Van Laere K, Novoveska L, Robbens J (2024) Genetic Engineering and Innovative Cultivation Strategies for Enhancing the Lutein Production in Microalgae. *Marine Drugs* 22(8), 329
- Cruz JD, Vasconcelos V (2024) Legal Aspects of Microalgae in the European Food Sector. *Foods* 13(1), 1
- Dagnaisser LS, dos Santos MGB, Rita AVS, Chaves Cardoso J, de Carvalho DF, de Mendonça HV (2022) Microalgae as Bio-fertilizer: a New Strategy for Advancing Modern Agriculture, Wastewater Bioremediation, and Atmospheric Carbon Mitigation. *Water Air Soil Pollut* 233(11), 477
- de Souza B, Magalhães VJ, Branco FJ (2021) Rumen fermentation and milk production responses to microalgae-based feed additives in dairy cows. *Animal Feed Science and Technology* 275, 114960
- Dibner JJ, Richards JD (2005) Antibiotic growth promoters in agriculture: History and mode of action. *Poultry Science* 84(4), 634–643
- EFSA Scientific Committee (2020) Evaluation of existing guidelines for their adequacy for the microbial characterisation and environmental risk assessment of microorganisms obtained through synthetic biology. *EFSA Journal* 18(10), e06263
- EFSA (2024) Public consultation on the 'draft guidance on the characterisation and risk assessment of microorganisms used in the food chain'. PC-1221 <https://connect.efsa.europa.eu/RM/s/consultations/publicconsultation2/a0ITk0000035F1V/pc1221>
- European Commission. (2003) Verordening (EG) Nr. 1831/2003 van het europees parlement en de raad van 22 september 2003 betreffende toevoegingsmiddelen voor diervoeding. In *Publicatieblad van de Europese Unie*: Vol. L 268
- European Commission (2018) Bioeconomy: the European way to use our natural resources. Action Plan.
- European Commission (2023). ANNEXES to the Proposal for a Regulation Of The European Parliament And Of The Council on plants obtained by certain new genomic techniques and their food and feed, and amending Regulation (EU) 2017/625

- European Commission (2021) Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions on a new approach for a sustainable blue economy in the EU transforming the EU's blue economy for a sustainable future. COM (2021) 240 final
- Gallego I, Medic N, Pedersen JS, Ramasamy PK, Robbens J, Vereecke E, Romeis J (2025) The microalgal sector in Europe: Towards a sustainable bioeconomy. *New Biot* 86, 1-13
- Hosseini-Vashan SJ, Golian A, Yaghobfar A, Namdari R (2020) Effects of dietary *Spirulina platensis* powder on egg quality, immune response, and oxidative status in laying hens. *Poultry Science* 99(3), 1551–1560
- Huang H, Lang Y, Zhou M (2024) A comprehensive review on medical applications of microalgae. *Algal research* 80(9), 103504
- Hwang J, Kim Y, Kim H (2020) Effects of *Chlorella vulgaris* supplementation on immune function and gut microbiota in weaned piglets. *Animal Bioscience* 33(9) 1476–1485
- Jeyamkondan S, Jayas DS, Holley RA (1999) Pulsed electric field processing of foods: a review. *Journal of Food Protection* 62(9), 1088–1096
- Khan Z, Bhadouria P, Bisen PS (2018) Nutritional and therapeutic potential of *Spirulina*. *Current Pharmaceutical Biotechnology* 19(9), 794–811
- Van Krimpen MM, Bikker P, Van der Meer IM, Van der Peet-Schwering CMC, Vereijken JM (2013) Cultivation, processing and nutritional aspects for pigs and poultry of European protein sources as alternatives for imported soybean products. Report 662, Wageningen UR livestock Research
- Liu M, Ding W, Yu L, Shi Y, Liu J (2022) Functional characterization of carotenogenic genes provides implications into carotenoid biosynthesis and engineering in the marine alga *Nannochloropsis oceanica*. *Algal Research* 67, 102853
- Lum KK, Kim J, Lei XG (2013) Dual potential of microalgae as a sustainable biofuel feedstock and animal feed. *Journal of Animal Science and Biotechnology* 4(1), 53
- Ma R, Zhang Z, Ho SH, Ruan C, Li J, Xie Y, Shi X, Liu L, Chen J (2020) Two-Stage Bioprocess for Hyper-Production of Lutein from Microalga *Chlorella Sorokiniana* FZU60: Effects of Temperature, Light Intensity, and Operation Strategies. *Algal Res.* 52, 102119
- Mullins E, Bresson JL, Dewhurst IC, Epstein MM, et al. (2024) New developments in biotechnology applied to microorganisms. *EFSA Journal* 22(7), e8895
- Murphy EJ, Rezoagli E, Collins C, Saha SK, Major I, Murray P (2023) Sustainable production and pharmaceutical applications of β -glucan from microbial sources. *Microbiological Research* 274, 127424
- Naduthodi MIS, Südfeld C, Avtiziannis EK, Trevisan N, Van Lith E, Sancho JA, D'Adamo S, Barbosa M, Van Der Oost J (2021) Comprehensive genome engineering toolbox for microalgae *Nannochloropsis oceanica* based on CRISPR-Cas systems. *ACS Synthetic Biology* 10(12), 3369-3378
- OECD-FAO (2021) Chapter 6: Meat. In *OECD-FAO Agricultural Outlook 2021-2030*
- Olsen MFL, Pedersen JS, Thomsen ST, Martens HJ, Pedersen A, Jensen PE (2021) Outdoor cultivation of a novel isolate of the microalgae *Scenedesmus* sp. And the evaluation of its potential as a novel protein crop. *Physiologia Plantarum* 173, 483-494
- Postma PR, Pataro G, Capitoli M, Barbosa MJ, Wijffels RH, Eppink MHM, Olivieri G, Ferrari G (2016) Selective extraction of intracellular components from the microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* by combined pulsed electric field-temperature treatment. *Bioresource Technology* 203, 80–88
- Purnhagen K, Ambrogio Y, Bartsch D, Eriksson D, Jorasch P, Kahrmann J, Kardung M, Molitorisová A, Monaco A, Nanda AK, Romeis J, Rostoks N, Unkel K, Schneider XT (2023) Options for regulating new genomic techniques for plants in the European Union. *Nat. Plants* 9(12), 1958-1691

- Reinhardt T, Monaco A (2025) How innovation-friendly is the EU novel food regulation? The case of cellular agriculture. *Future Foods* 11, 100574
- Ren Y, Sun H, Deng J, Huang J, Chen F (2021) Carotenoid production from microalgae: biosynthesis, salinity responses and novel biotechnologies. *Marine Drugs* 19(12), 713
- Rumin J, Gonçalves de Oliveira Junior R, Bérard JB, Picot L (2021) Improving Microalgae Research and Marketing in the European Atlantic Area: Analysis of Major Gaps and Barriers Limiting Sector Development. *Marine Drugs* 19(6), 6
- Safi C, Zebib B, Merah O, Pontalier PY, Vaca-Garcia C (2014) Morphology, composition, production, processing and applications of *Chlorella vulgaris*: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 35, 265–278
- Schwarm A, Schweigel-Röntgen M, Kreuzer M (2016) Effects of microalgae supplementation on milk fatty acid profiles in dairy cows. *Journal of Dairy Science* 99(8), 6216–6225
- Shah MR, Lutz GA, Alam A, et al. (2018) Microalgae in aquafeeds for a sustainable aquaculture industry. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 30(4), 1975–1999
- Van Nerom S, Coleman B, De Baets R, Van Immerseel F, Robbens J, Delezie E (2024a) Microalgae as feed additives in poultry: A review on the health-promoting effects. *Algal Research*. 83, 103733
- Van Nerom S, Buyse K, Van Immerseel F, Robbens J, Delezie E (2024b) Pulsed electric field (PEF) processing of microalga *Chlorella vulgaris* and its digestibility in broiler feed. *Poultry Science*. 103(6), 103721
- Van Nerom S, Buyse K, Van Immerseel F, Robbens J, Delezie E (2025) Exploring Feed Digestibility and Broiler Performance in Response to Dietary Supplementation of *Chlorella vulgaris*. *Animals* 15(1), 1
- Wesseler J, Kleter G, Meulenbroek M, Purnhagen KP (2023) EU regulation of genetically modified microorganisms in light of new policy developments: Possible implications for EU bioeconomy investments. *Applied Economic Perspectives and Policy* 45:839–859
- Xie Y, Zhang Z, Ma R, Liu X, Miao M, Ho SH, Chen J, Leong YK, Chang JS (2022) High-Cell-Density Heterotrophic Cultivation of Microalga *Chlorella Sorokiniana* FZU60 for Achieving Ultra-High Lutein Production Efficiency. *Bioresour. Technol.* 365, 128130
- Yadav AS, Kolluri G, Gopi M, Karthik K, Malik YS, Dhama K. (2016) Exploring alternatives to antibiotics as health promoting agents in poultry- a review. *Journal of Experimental Biology and Agricultural Sciences* 4(3S), 368–383
- Wang Q, Lu Y, Xin Y, Wei L, Huang S, Xu J (2016) Genome editing of model oleaginous microalgae *Nannochloropsis* spp. By CRISPR/Cas9. *Plant J* 88(6), 1071-1081
- Wu K, Lai J, Zhang Q, Wang Y, Cui X, Liu Y, Wu X, Yu Z, Ruan R (2024) Optimizing *Chlorella vulgaris* cultivation to enhance biomass and lutein production. *Foods* 13(16), 2514

European Regulations and Directives:

- Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2015 on novel foods, amending Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Regulation (EC) No 258/97 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1852/2001; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02015R2283-20210327>
- Directive 2002/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 10 June 2002 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to food supplements; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02002L0046-20240717>
- Regulation No 767/2009/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 July 2009 on the placing on the market and use of feed, amending European Parliament and Council Regulation No 1831/2003/EC and repealing Council Directive 79/373/EEC, Commission Directive 80/511/EEC,

- Council Directives 82/471/EEC, 83/228/EEC, 93/74/EEC, 93/113/EC and 96/25/EC and Commission Decision 2004/217/EC; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02009R0767-20181226>
- Directive 2009/41/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 May 2009 on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2009/41/oj/eng>
 - Regulation No 1829/2003/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 22 September 2003 on genetically modified food and feed; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02003R1829-20210327>
 - Directive 2001/18/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 March 2001 on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms and repealing Council Directive 90/220/EEC; <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02001L0018-20210327>
 - Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 November 2015 on novel foods, amending Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011 of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Regulation (EC) No 258/97 of the European Parliament and of the Council and Commission Regulation (EC) No 1852/2001, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2015/2283/oj/eng>

About GeneBEcon

GeneBEcon – Capturing the potential of Gene editing for a sustainable BioEconomy

GeneBEcon is an ambitious Horizon Europe-funded project, which examines the innovation potential of gene editing to enable a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe. Through the application of this technology in potato and microalgae, GeneBEcon intends to promote energy-efficient, low-input, and zero-pollution agricultural production and clean industrial processing.

New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) represent a powerful toolbox which is complementary to traditional breeding techniques and contributes to alleviating current pressing challenges such as pollution and climate change. However, these techniques do not yet reach their full potential in Europe. GeneBEcon will advance research and innovation, acting on two fronts: through new gene editing developments at the technological level, as well as considering social, economic, and regulatory dimensions.

Among NGTs, gene editing holds the greatest potential for contributing to the ambitious objectives of the European Green Deal, the 2030 Climate Target Plan, and the Circular Economy Action Plan. Nonetheless, risks and benefits must be assessed to ensure that gene editing innovations, just like any other type of innovation, are developed in a responsible, inclusive, and transparent way. GeneBEcon aims to address these concerns and propel Europe towards a cleaner, more sustainable and zero-pollution agricultural and industrial production.

GeneBEcon will construct a toolbox for gene editing using potato and microalgae as case studies and it will assess regulatory options in terms of data requirements for risk assessment, analyse the economic impact and consider societal perceptions. The gene-edited potato will be virus-resistant to enable reduced use of pesticides in potato cultivation, and it will produce a higher quality starch allowing a more environmentally friendly potato starch processing saving up to 75,000 tonnes of chemicals and 7.5 GWh of energy in the EU every year. Likewise, gene-edited microalgae will allow resource-efficient and clean production of industrially relevant compounds and the repurposing of microalgae residual biomass as animal feed.

GeneBEcon has a budget of 5.5 million Euros and a duration of three years as of 1 September, 2022. GeneBEcon is executed by a multidisciplinary consortium with leading scientists from 11 European countries and in interdisciplinary collaboration with stakeholders.

Partners:

Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences,
Sweden – Project Coordinator
XPRO Consulting Limited, Cyprus
SolEdits AB, Sweden
Latvijas Universitate, Latvia
FN3PT/inov3PT, France
INRAE, France
Euroseeds, Belgium
Danish Technological Institute, Denmark
Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra,
Slovakia

EV ILVO, Belgium
Plants for the Future ETP, Belgium
Wageningen University, the Netherlands
BVL, Germany
Universität Bayreuth, Germany
Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação, Portugal
HZPC Research BV, the Netherlands
INVE Belgie, Belgium
Associated Partner:
WBF-Agroscope, Switzerland

For more information, please contact:

Dennis ERIKSSON, Project Coordinator

Department of Plant Breeding, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden

E-mail: dennis.eriksson@slu.se

Website: <https://www.slu.se/en/ew-cv/dennis-eriksson/>